

Magic wavelengths for $^1S_0 \leftrightarrow ^3P_1$ transition in Sr.

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Here I briefly overview different magic wavelengths for different polarizations, robustness of these magic conditions, and scattering rates of magic light for $^1S_0 \rightarrow ^3P_1$ transitions in Sr.

I. INTRODUCTION. LIGHT SHIFTS AND SCATTERING RATES

Magic wavelength of the optical lattice is a wavelength where the light shifts of both the upper and the lower clock states are the same. Theory of the light shifts is presented in many sources, see, for example, [?] and references therein. Here we are interested in the magic wavelengths for $^1S_0 \leftrightarrow ^3P_1(m=0)$ transition of ^{88}Sr atom. In present overview, we consider light shifts of the atom in monochromatic running-wave polarized field with angular frequency ω and wavelength λ :

$$\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{E_0}{2} \left(\vec{\varepsilon} e^{i(\vec{k}\vec{r} - \omega t)} + c.c. \right)$$

A. Light shift and scattering rates

The **light shift** depends on the polarization of the light field, if only angular momenta of the upper and the lower states aren't both zeros. This light shift of the state $|i\rangle$ can be writtern (in Gaussian unit system) as

$$LS_c = -\alpha_c(\lambda, \vec{\varepsilon}) \frac{E_0^2}{4} = -\alpha_c(\lambda, \vec{\varepsilon}) \frac{2\pi I}{c}, \quad (1)$$

where E_0 is the amplitude, and I is the intensity of the light, c is the speed of light, and $\alpha_c(\lambda, \vec{\varepsilon})$ is the polarizability of the state $|c\rangle$ depending on the wavelength λ and polarization vector $\vec{\varepsilon}$ of the light. This shift may be expressed as

$$\alpha_c(\lambda, \vec{\varepsilon}) = \sum_k \frac{2\omega_{kc}}{\hbar(\omega_{kc}^2 - \omega^2)} \sum_{p=-1}^1 \varepsilon^{p2} \cdot |\langle k | \hat{d}_{1p} | c \rangle|^2. \quad (2)$$

Here ε^p is the p th contravariant component of polarization vector $\vec{\varepsilon}$, $\langle k | \hat{d}_{1p} | c \rangle$ is the matrix element of p th covariant cyclic component of dipole momentum operator [?]:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^{\pm 1} &= \mp \frac{\varepsilon_x \mp i\varepsilon_y}{\sqrt{2}}; & \varepsilon^0 &= \varepsilon_z \\ \hat{d}_{1\pm 1} &= \mp \frac{\hat{d}_x \pm i\hat{d}_y}{\sqrt{2}}; & \hat{d}_{10} &= \hat{d}_z \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The **scattering rate** of far-detuned light accompanied by transition of the atom from state $|a\rangle$ into state $|b\rangle$ can be written as

$$\Gamma_{\text{sc}, a \rightarrow b} = \frac{I \sigma_{\text{sc}, a \rightarrow b}}{\hbar \omega} \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{sc}, a \rightarrow b}$ is the partial scattering cross-section given by the Kramers-Heisenberg formula [? ?]; see derivation in [? ?]

$$\sigma_{\text{sc}, a \rightarrow b} = \frac{8\pi}{3} \frac{I \omega'^3 \omega}{c^4 \hbar^3} \sum_{q=-1}^1 |D_q|^2, \quad \text{where}$$

$$D_q = \sum_{k,p} \varepsilon^p \left[\frac{\langle b | \hat{d}_{1q} | k \rangle \langle k | \hat{d}_{1p} | a \rangle}{\omega_{ka} - \omega} + \frac{\langle b | \hat{d}_{1p} | k \rangle \langle k | \hat{d}_{1q} | a \rangle}{\omega_{ka} + \omega'} \right], \quad (5)$$

where $\omega' = \omega - \omega_{ba}$ is the frequency of outgoing photon (we neglect recoil here), and $|k\rangle$ are intermediate states what have dipole-allowed connections with states $|a\rangle$ and $|b\rangle$.

- *Rayleigh scattering* is a scattering when the atom returns into its initial state ($|a\rangle = |b\rangle$). Such a process does not affect the coherence on the clock transition, if the scattering light has the magic frequency [?].
- *Raman scattering* is a scattering when the atom changes its states, i.e., when $|a\rangle \neq |b\rangle$. This scattering leads to decoherence and depopulation of the upper state.
- We consider here only the scattering from $|5s5p^3P_1, m=1\rangle$ state into different sublevels of $5s5p^3P_J$ manifold, because other channels will be suppressed due to scaling with ω'^3 . Also, $|5s5s^1S_0\rangle$ state expect almost only the Rayleigh scattering due to the same reason.

B. Matrix elements of dipole momentum operators

For correct calculation of the scattering rate, interference of different paths leading into the same final state should be accounted for correctly. Therefore, it is important to keep the signs of products like $\langle b | \hat{d}_{1q} | k \rangle \langle k | \hat{d}_{1p} | a \rangle$ in (??). We express matrix elements $\langle c | \hat{d}_{1r} | k \rangle$ as (see [?], eq. (B.9))

$$\langle c | \hat{d}_{1r} | k \rangle = \langle nSLJm | \hat{d}_{1r} | n'SL'J'm' \rangle = \sqrt{\frac{3\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar c^3 A_{T,n'J'}}{\tilde{\omega}_{n'J'}^3}} \sqrt{(2J'+1)(2L'+1)(2J+1)} \times$$

$$(-1)^{2J'+L+S-m} \times \begin{Bmatrix} L & L' & 1 \\ J' & J & S \end{Bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & J' & J \\ p & m' & -m \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Here $|c\rangle = |nSLJm\rangle$, $|k\rangle = |n'SL'J'm'\rangle$, $|a\rangle = |nSLJm\rangle$ is a general notation for $|a\rangle$ and $|b\rangle$; r is a general notation for p and q ; n, n' are principal quantum numbers, S is the total electron spin (in our case $S = 1$ in all the states $|c\rangle$ and $|k\rangle$), L, L' are the orbital momenta, J, J' are total electron momenta, and m, m' are projections of these momenta respectively; $A_{T,n'J'}$ is the total spontaneous decay rate from the level $|k\rangle$ characterized by principal quantum number n' and electronic angular momentum J' into the whole $5s5p^3P_J$ manifold, and $\tilde{\omega}_{n'J'}$ is the weighted

average of transition frequency from state $|k\rangle$ into the $5s5p^3P_J$ manifold:

$$\tilde{\omega}_{n'J'}^3 = \sum_J \omega_{n'J' \rightarrow nJ}^3 (2J+1)(2L'+1) \left\{ \begin{matrix} L & L' & 1 \\ J' & J & S \end{matrix} \right\}^2 \quad (7)$$

To calculate matrix elements $\langle k|\hat{d}_{1r}|c\rangle$, one can use the relation following from the definition of cyclic orts (??).

$$\langle k|\hat{d}_{1r}|c\rangle = (-1)^r \langle c|\hat{d}_{1-r}|k\rangle. \quad (8)$$

Remark about calculation of matrix elements from the data given in [?]

In [?], the values of A_T , i.e., the *total* transition rates from the *whole upper* fine-structure manifold into the lower one are given instead of $A_{T,n'J'}$. These rates are defined as (in Gaussian unit system)

$$A_T = \frac{4\tilde{\omega}_{n'L'}^3}{3\hbar c^3} \frac{\langle n'L'|\hat{d}_1|nL\rangle}{2L'+1}, \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{\omega}_{n'L'}$ is defined as “the energy difference between two fine-structure manifold states” [?], and $\langle n'L'|\hat{d}_1|nL\rangle$ is the co-called *reduced matrix element* of dipole momentum what may be used for calculation of its matrix element. Unfortunately, there were no any more accurate definition of this frequency as well as the definition of A_T (because such a value is just a some kind of weighted averaged of $A_{T,n'J'}$, but the weights should be known). However, authors of [?] refers to the paper [?], where the weights in the averaging of $A_{T,n'J'}$ are chosen to be proportional to $2J'+1$. It gives

$$\tilde{\omega}_{n'L'}^3 = \frac{1}{(2L'+1)(2S'+1)} \sum_{J'} (2J'+1) \tilde{\omega}_{n'J'}^3. \quad (10)$$

Calculation of matrix elements according to abovementioned procedure leads, however, to the values of A_J what differs from the ones given in [?] in 3rd digit. But it does not affected significantly the results.

Intercombination line

I have taken into account also the *intercombination line transition* $|5s5s^1S_0\rangle \leftrightarrow |5s5p^3P_1\rangle$ as

$$\langle 5s5s^1S_0|\hat{d}_{1r}|5s5p^3P_1, m'\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{3\hbar c^3}{4\omega^3}} 3A_{n'J' \rightarrow nJ} C_{1m'1r}^{00}. \quad (11)$$

This line does not affect the characteristics of the magic wavelength significantly, but slightly shifts these magic wavelengths.

II. POLARIZATION OF THE LIGHT

There are 2 different “ideal” types of polarization of the light: π -polarization (can be realized, only if the quantization axis z (given by magnetic field) is ortogonal to wave vector \vec{k} of the electromagnetic field), and xy - polarization, when the electromagnetic field is ortogonal to the quantization axis. Linear polarization in (x, y) -plane, and circular polarization are particular cases of this type. These types are presented on the sketch below:

III. LIGHT SHIFTS FOR “PURE” POLARIZATIONS

Light shifts for different polarizations (black for ground and red for excited states, “magic points” are marked by blue circles):

xy-polarization

Here we have magic wavelengths at $\lambda = 914$ nm, $\lambda = 500$ nm, $\lambda = 480$ nm and $\lambda = 473.14$ nm

π-polarization

For π -polarization magic wavelengths are: $\lambda = 513$ nm, $\lambda = 485$ nm and $\lambda = 473.38$ nm.

IV. IMPERFECT POLARIZATION

We can imagine ideal linear polarization of the field, i.e., the absence of any predominance of left-rotating wave over the right-rotating, or vice versa. However, even in such a case the polarization of the light will be always imperfect, because ideal alignment of the magnetic field \vec{B} with the polarization vector \vec{E}_0 and/or propagation vector

\vec{k} is inattainable. One can introduce angle φ between \vec{E}_0 and \vec{B} : $\varphi = 0$ for ideal π -polarization, and $\varphi = \pi/2$ for ideal xy -polarization.

Polarizability for linearly polarized light at arbitrary φ can be expressed as

$$\alpha_\varphi(i, \phi, \lambda) = \frac{\alpha(i, 1, \lambda) + \alpha(i, -1, \lambda)}{2} \sin^2 \varphi + \alpha(i, 0, \lambda) \cos^2 \varphi. \quad (12)$$

So, the contribution of the polarizability with undesirable component is proportional to the *squared* deviation of the angle φ from 0 or $\pi/2$.

Sketches of appearance of the angle φ in different geometries are shown below:

Therefore, one may note that the most controllable is the geometry where the wave vector \vec{k} is co-aligned with the magnetic field \vec{B} , because in such a case, $\frac{\pi}{2} - \varphi$ can be turned to zero by tuning of two angles θ and ϕ .

V. CHARACTERIZATION OF MAGIC WAVELENGTHS

It is convenient to use μK as a units of the trap depth, and s^{-1} as a units of differential shifts. We will use the following parameters for characterization of the magic wavelengths:

- λ , nm — magic wavelength;
- $\frac{U}{I}$, $\frac{\mu K \times \text{cm}^2}{\text{kW}}$ — trap depth to intensity;
- $\frac{\gamma_{\text{sc,Rm}}}{U}$, $\frac{s^{-1}}{\mu K}$ — Raman scattering rate to trap depth (i.e., to $5s5p^3P_0$, $5s5p^3P_2$, and $5s5p^3P_1$, $m = \pm 1$ states);
- $\frac{d\Delta_{LS}}{U d\lambda}$, $\frac{s^{-1}}{\mu K \times \text{nm}}$ — sensitivity of differential light shift Δ_{LS} to variation of the wavelength at unit trap depth;
- $\frac{d^2\Delta_{LS}}{U d\varphi^2}$, $\frac{s^{-1}}{\mu K \times \text{deg}^2}$ — sensitivity of differential light shift Δ_{LS} to variation of the polarization angle φ at unit trap depth;

Magic wavelengths are summarized below:

pol.	λ , nm	$\frac{U}{I}$, $\frac{\mu\text{K} \times \text{cm}^2}{\text{kW}}$	$\frac{\gamma_{\text{sc,Rm}}}{U}$, $\frac{\text{s}^{-1}}{\mu\text{K}}$	$\frac{d\Delta_{LS}}{Ud\lambda}$, $\frac{\text{s}^{-1}}{\mu\text{K} \times \text{nm}}$	$\frac{d^2\Delta_{LS}}{Ud\varphi^2}$, $\frac{\text{s}^{-1}}{\mu\text{K} \times \text{deg}^2}$
xy -pol.	913.23	0.57	0.0041	-250	-20
	499.68	2.8	0.0223	-6.4×10^3	15.7
	479.83	5.4	2.03	-1.47×10^5	-99.7
	473.144	8.17	3.22	-2.31×10^5	16.86
π -pol.	513.28	2.17	0.00187	-1.93×10^3	-13.5
	485.27	4.27	4.06	-3.49×10^5	-123
	473.378	8.02	2.56	-185×10^5	-12.9

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